

MECHANICAL RESPONSE OF PARTICLE-FILLED POLYETHYLENE ON ELECTRICALLY GENERATED THERMAL SHOCK PULSE

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SUMMARY: Highly conducting metal-filled polyethylene with positive temperature coefficient (PTC) of resistivity have been prepared and exposed to strong transient current pulses. Caused by the strong non-linear change of resistivity with temperature, a narrow hot-zone is formed in the center part of the test samples. The resistivity switches by eight orders of magnitude and interrupts the current flow. The thermally stimulated mechanical shock pulse is monitored with a laser distance sensor system and the surface temperature development by an infrared camera. The combined results of electrical, mechanical and temperature measurement are used to determine extension and Young's Modulus of the hot-zone.

KEYWORDS: positive temperature coefficient of resistivity, electrical conductivity, thermal expansion, thermal imaging, mechanical response, polymer composite

INTRODUCTION

In order to meet the needs of industry for materials with new and suitable electrical, mechanical and thermal properties, the interest in composites is more and more increasing. One class of functional composites are polymers which are filled with particles having tailored properties. Such kind of materials can combine flexibility, lightweight, low cost and simple processability of polymeric materials with an additionally desired functionality of the filler material as, e.g., high electrical [1] or thermal conductivity [2], polarizability [3], magnetic [4] or non-linear dielectric properties [5,6].

Carbon black or metal filled polymers show, for example, a positive temperature coefficient (PTC) of the electrical resistivity. Therefore, they are widely used as self-regulating heating tapes [7] or circuit protecting devices [8,9]. Such polymer based composites with PTC behavior are also interesting systems in order to study the correlation between thermal, mechanical and electrical properties of composites in general. The thermal energy is generated mainly close to the contact points of the conducting filler particles. Due to the high thermal conductivity of the filler particles, they heat up first. Then the surrounding polymer is heated too and expands due to its relatively large thermal expansion coefficient. The thermal expansion works against internal mechanical stresses, which have been built up during the preparation of the sample, until a certain expansion has been achieved. Then a strong change in resistivity is observed caused by changes in gap distance of the particle-particle contacts in the expanded matrix. This view is supported by measurements on metal particles in epoxy [10] and holds for a thermoplastic matrix as well. A similar explanation has been given by Carmona et al. for carbon fibers in epoxy [11].

For applications under severe conditions (i.e. high current or electrical field, elevated temperature and mechanical shock), it is important to understand the dynamic correlation between electrical, thermal and mechanical properties of such composites in order to find their physical limits. It has been shown recently, that the filler particle size has a strong influence on the tripping dynamic under high current load. The PTC material trips faster, the smaller the particles are [12].

In the present paper, the strong nonlinearity of the resistivity with temperature is utilized to generate a thermo-mechanical shock wave. When a strong current is applied to the PTC material, it is heated very fast by Joule's losses. Due to the nonlinearity of the resistivity, it becomes even faster and concentrates on hot-spots. The temperature increase gives rise to a rapid thermal expansion of the polymer and results in a thermo-mechanical shock wave. This is accompanied by a resistance increases of several orders of magnitude, which interrupts the current flow. The motion of the sample, detected by a laser interferometer system, and the current are measured simultaneously. The amplitude of the expansion is related to the extension of the hot-zone and the thermal expansion coefficient of the composite. The frequency of the oscillation can be correlated to the Young's Modulus of the hot composite and the total accelerated mass of the test samples.

MATERIAL PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION

The active body of the PTC-samples is a polymer-metal composite consisting of 50 vol.-% of highly conducting TiB_2 particles in different polyethylene matrixes (see Table 1). In order to achieve a homogeneous dispersion, filler and matrix material were compounded for several minutes by using a Brabender Plasticorder at temperatures around 180°C . After compounding the composites were hot-pressed at 145°C and 11 MPa to form several mm thick plates. The dependence of the electrical resistivity of the composite material on the temperature was determined by using an HP 4247 A Impedance Analyzer. The small test samples had sizes of 20mm·10mm·2mm and were measured in four-probe geometry.

Fig. 1 shows the behavior of the resistivity ρ as a function of temperature for a heating and a succeeding cooling run of the composite with high-density polyethylene (HDPE5261Z) as matrix material. The resistivity increases by eight orders of magnitude from about $10^{-2}\Omega\text{cm}$ at ambient room temperature to more than $10^6\Omega\text{cm}$ at 140°C . After cooling, the resistivity comes back to almost the same value as before heating, i.e. the PTC effect is repetitive.

The temperature dependence of ρ between 30 and 120°C is weak. Around 135°C , however, a strong increase of seven orders of magnitude in ρ occurs within a narrow temperature range of only 15°C . The strong step in resistivity is observed close to the melting temperature $T_m = 134^\circ\text{C}$, as expected [1], and can be associated with the strong non-linear temperature dependent thermal expansion of the polyethylene matrix near its melting temperature [13]. The strong nonlinearity of $\rho(T)$ can be expected as the driving force for the creation of only one localized hot-zone in one composite PTC element. The thermal expansion of e.g. high-density polyethylene HDPE5231, filled with 50 vol.-% TiB_2 , was measured by dilatometry as shown in Fig. 2. The thermal expansion coefficient α is defined by the slope of the curve and exhibits a strong increase when approaching the melting temperature of the matrix material. The composite material loses mechanical strength at elevated temperatures which restricts the measurement of $\alpha(T)$ by dilatometry to temperatures below the melting temperature.

Table 1: Important material parameters at $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$ are listed for two high density polyethylene materials; Melting temperature (T_{melt}), specific heat (c), specific melting enthalpy (c_{melt}), thermal conductivity (λ), mass density (ρ), Young's Modulus (E), tensile strength (E_{tensile}) and thermal expansion coefficient (α) between 20 and 80°C .

↓ property ; material ⇒	HDPE5231	HDPE5261Z
T_{melt} ($^\circ\text{C}$)	133	134
c (J/gK)	1.9	1.7
c_{melt} (J/g)	165	200
λ (W/Km)	0.37	0.41
ρ (g/cm ³)	0.952	0.954
E (GPa)	1.1	1.3
E_{tensile} (MPa)	25	27
α (20-80 $^\circ\text{C}$) ($10^{-6}/\text{K}$)	150-180	130-160

Fig. 1: The specific resistivity ρ of 50 vol.-% TiB_2 filled high density polyethylene HDPE5261Z as a function of temperature for one heating/cooling cycle, which was done within three hours.

Fig. 2: The relative thermal expansion $\Delta l/l$ of 50 vol.-% TiB_2 filled high density polyethylene of type HDPE5231 as a function of temperature.

TEST SAMPLES

A side-view sketch of the used sample arrangement is shown in Fig. 3a. The sample consists of an about 2 mm thick plate of the composite material with aluminum contacts, which are pressed onto the composite. The press contacts are mounted by flexible brass plates. A ceramic varistor disc is fixed and pressed between the two brass plates together to form a good electrical connection to the PTC element.

In order to make sure that the sample trips in the center part of the PTC element, the cross-section of the PTC-body is simply reduced by holes. This technique to define a tripping zone by reduced cross-section, is well known and already industrially used [14,15]. A top view of the composite body with the aluminum contacts is seen in Fig. 3b.

The total resistance R_{PTC}^{cold} of the sample comprises the resistance of the composite plate between the contacts R_{cold} , plus the contact resistance $R_{contact}$ between the composite material and the metal contacts but without the negligible resistance of the brass terminals themselves.

$$R_{PTC}^{cold} = R_{cold} + R_{contact} = 1.0832 \cdot \frac{\rho \cdot l}{A} + R_{contact} \quad (1)$$

where A is the cross-section of the PTC plate, l is the length of the PTC plate between the electrodes, $R_{contact}$ is the contact resistance between the PTC-body and the press contacts, and ρ is the specific resistivity of the PTC composite well below T_c . The factor 1.0832 results from the particular sample geometry.

Fig. 3: (a) The sample set-up of the PTC composite resistor (very left), connected in parallel to a spacer, which provides mechanical stability and a ceramic varistor disc (top right in (a)). The incident and reflection direction of the laser beam and the direction of the motion of the expansion (Δz) are also indicated. (b) Sketch of PTC-body and the contacts as seen from top.

ELECTRICAL MEASUREMENTS

The electrical arrangement to generate the high and fast increasing current through the PTC composite sample is realized with a low impedance capacitor bank. The circuit lay-out is given in Fig. 4. The varistor limits over-voltages in the circuit which are generated during the resistance change of the PTC composite. The relevant circuit parameters are: $C = 14.6\text{mF}$, $L = 54\mu\text{H}$, which give rise to $I_{max} = 4.9\text{kA}$ at a frequency of 179 Hz for a loading voltage $U = 300\text{V}$.

Fig. 4: Sketch of the used electrical circuit for generating the high current pulse through the composite material. The circuit parameters are: Capacitor $C = 14.6\text{mF}$, Inductance $L = 54\mu\text{H}$.

Fig. 5: Thermal image of 50 vol.-% TiB_2 filled HDPE5261Z material 100ms after tripping. The insert in the upper part shows the temperature distribution along the line perpendicular to the current flow direction.

EXPANSION MEASUREMENT

A commercially available laser distance sensor, Type: Keyence LC-2400A, is used for the detection of the dynamic expansion of the PTC resistor during the high current flow and its limitation. The principle of measurement bases on optical triangulation and is described elsewhere [16,17]. The distance signal is calibrated and directly available as an analogue output signal (for example: 1V for $10\mu\text{m}$). For the described experiments a resolution of $0.5\mu\text{m}$ and a sampling rate of 50 kHz is obtained with the optical sensor. In order to avoid disturbing mechanical resonance oscillations, the expansion is measured in some cases with one fixed contact. The expansion of the entire composite plate is detected at the polished surface of one flexible contact about 3 mm apart from the sample's axis. Therefore a multiple correction factor of 1.12 has to be taken into account to get the right Δz -amplitude.

With the simultaneous measurement of dynamic expansion and current flow through the PTC composite it is possible to demonstrate on a μs -timescale how the current limitation is correlated to the thermal expansion.

THERMAL IMAGING

During the experiments thermal images of the sample surface are recorded at video frequency (i.e. 30 pictures/s) by an infrared detection system (Nippon Avionics Co. Ltd., TVS-2200ST). With this method the surface temperature of the PTC sample can be monitored and provides additional information to estimate approximately the size and the shape of the region where the PTC trips. In Fig. 5 a typical image of an infrared picture is shown, which was taken 90 to 120 ms after the current flow through the PTC element was started.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Fig. 6 measurements of the current and voltage response (top part) and the energy input into the PTC element and the parallel varistor (bottom part) are given. Current flow starts at $t_0 = 1.45\text{ms}$ and heats up the PTC sample. The PTC sample warms up, increases its resistance which is accompanied by a voltage drop across the sample. At $t = 2.1\text{ms}$ the maximum resistance is reached, the current is commuted to the parallel varistor according to its voltage-current characteristic, and the current through the PTC element is suppressed nearly to zero. At $t_{\text{end}} = 2.8\text{ms}$, i.e. approximately 1.35ms after the start of experiment, no current can be detected anymore.

The energy input into the PTC element (E_{PTC}) and the varistor (E_{VAR}), as plotted in Fig. 6, are calculated by Eqn 2

$$E = E_{\text{PTC}} + E_{\text{VAR}} = \int_{t_0}^{t_{\text{end}}} I_{\text{PTC}} \cdot U \cdot dt + \int_{t_0}^{t_{\text{end}}} I_{\text{VAR}} \cdot U \cdot dt \quad (2)$$

where I_{PTC} and I_{VAR} are the currents through PTC element and varistor, U is the voltage across them, and t_0 and t_{end} are the times when current flow starts and ends, respectively. The input energies are typically 150J for the PTC element and 250J for the parallel varistor.

The particular sample geometry with reduced cross-section in the center part of the PTC-body gives rise to a well defined tripping region. The temperature distribution at the PTC sample surface, as recorded just 100 ms after current flow start, is displayed in Fig. 5. Only a narrow zone of the PTC-body with an extension of few mm in current flow direction seems to be heated up sufficiently high for the PTC effect to take place. Therefore, three different regions of energy input during current flow can be localized. The contact region close at and also under the aluminum contacts, the PTC-body with constant cross-section, and the center part of the PTC-body with reduced cross-section. When a current is applied to the PTC sample, it is heated by Joule's losses with the power

$$P(t) = U(t) \cdot I_{\text{PTC}} = R_{\text{PTC}}(t) \cdot (I_{\text{PTC}}(t))^2 \quad (3)$$

and the total energy input into the PTC sample can be calculated with Eqn 4

$$E_{\text{PTC}} = \int_{t_0}^{t_{\text{end}}} R(t)_{\text{PTC}} \cdot (I(t)_{\text{PTC}})^2 \cdot dt \quad (4)$$

where $R_{\text{PTC}}(t)$ and $I_{\text{PTC}}(t)$ are the time dependent total resistance and current of the composite sample. With respect to the sample geometry, Eqn 4 can be split into three single contributions, i.e. the contribution of the contact (E_{contact}), of constant cross-section (E_{side}) and of reduced cross-section (E_{center}) as formulated in Eqns 5 and 6

$$E_{\text{PTC}} = E_{\text{contact}} + E_{\text{side}} + E_{\text{center}} \quad (5)$$

$$E_{\text{PTC}} = \int_{t_0}^{t_{\text{end}}} \left[(R_{\text{contact}} + R_{\text{cold}} + \sum_{n=1}^k (\rho_n(T(t)) - \rho) \cdot \frac{l_n}{A_n}) \cdot (I_{\text{PTC}})^2 \right] \cdot dt \quad (6)$$

where R_{contact} is the contact resistance, R_{cold} is the resistance of the entire PTC-body at room temperature (25°C), ρ is the specific resistance at room temperature, $\rho_n(T(t))$ is the time and temperature dependent specific resistivity of a volume element ($l_n \cdot A_n$) inside the hot-zone, A_n is the cross-section of a n^{th} volume element of the length l_n in current flow direction and finally I_{PTC} is the current through the PTC element.

Fig. 6: Upper part: Voltage across PTC element (Voltage), varistor current (VAR-Current), current through the PTC element (PTC-Current) and total current (TOT-Current), as mentioned in the foot line, are displayed in the relevant time window. The current flow starts at $t_0 = 1.45\text{ms}$. Bottom part: The energy input into the PTC element (PTC-Energy), the varistor (VAR-Energy) and the total input energy (TOT-Energy) as calculated from the measured voltage and currents of the upper part.

Eqns 5 and 6 determine the energy input into the three regions separately. The result for a PTC element with HDPE5261Z matrix is seen in Table 2, with $k = 20$ and all l_n of same length, $R_{\text{contact}} = 11.1\text{ m}\Omega$ and $R_{\text{cold}} = 27\text{ m}\Omega$, with the $\rho(T)$ -characteristic from Fig. 1 and a current response as seen in Fig. 6 (top part). It is observed that a major part of the energy is deposited in the region of constant cross-section. A rough estimation of the temperature development of the parts of constant and reduced cross-section can be done by assuming adiabatic conditions during heating up within few ms, i.e. there is no energy exchange with the surrounding. The entire electrical energy (E_{input}) is used to heat the parts of the PTC from a starting temperature T_{start} to an end temperature T_{end} homogeneously. Eqn 7 is applied for both regions separately with different m and T_{end} and a specific heat $c(T)$ of weak temperature dependence.

$$E_{input} = \int_{T_{start}}^{T_{end}} m \cdot c(T) \cdot dT \quad \text{with} \quad \Delta T_{max} = T_{end} - T_{start} \quad (7)$$

The PTC part of reduced cross-section is heated above melting temperature, thus an additional melting enthalpy of about 200J/g for the polyethylene has to be taken into account. The resulting average temperature increase is listed in Table 2. Although the temperature increase of the part of constant cross-section is only 45°C, the major part of the energy is deposited in this region. A smaller energy input of 41J into the middle part is sufficient to bring the PTC element into the high-resistive state.

The results are in good agreement with the measured input energy into the PTC element as seen in Fig. 6 and the surface temperature development as seen from Fig. 5.

Table 2: For the three different regions of the PTC sample the resulting input energies and the maximum average temperature increase ΔT_{max} are listed.

part of the PTC sample	Input-Energy (J)	ΔT_{max} (°C)
contact region	26	-
constant cross-section	73	45
reduced cross-section	41	125
entire PTC sample	140	> 45

In Fig. 7 the dynamic expansion of a test sample (full line) and the current through it (dashed line) are shown within a time window of 10ms. The current starts to increase with a slope of about 5kA/ms at $t_0 = 1.45$ ms, reaches the maximum value of 2.3kA about 0.6ms later and is suppressed nearly to zero at $t_{end} = 2.3$ ms. Of course, even after this time, there is still a residual current in the mA-range, which is high enough to keep the sample in the high-resistive state. This current is mainly determined by the external cooling conditions and the $\rho(T)$ -characteristic.

It is interesting to note that the short-circuit current is limited long before the element reaches its final expansion. The expansion starts at $t = 1.75$ ms and reaches at $t = 2.9$ ms a maximum elongation of 65 μ m. After reaching the maximum expansion, mechanical oscillations are observed around the new stable position of the sample at about 50 μ m elongation.

The thermal energy is supposed to be generated mainly close to the contact points of the conducting filler particles. Due to the low thermal conductivity of the polymer, a time delay of about one ms between the maximum of the current and the thermal expansion of the composite is observed. The resistivity increase by the mechanical separation of the conducting filler particles is obviously high enough to suppress the current to about zero long before the full expansion is achieved.

The thermal images, which were taken 100ms later, show a hot-zone which expands over the entire sample cross-section perpendicular to current flow direction. In current flow direction, the hot-zone is strongly localized to a narrow region of only a few mm. Thus, as already confirmed in the previous section, the tripped PTC-body can be divided into a cold part with $T_{low} \ll T_c$ and a hot part with $T_{high} \approx T_c$.

The extension of the hot-zone can be determined by analyzing the thermal images and the thermal expansion into the new stable Δz -position of the PTC sample. The linear one dimensional thermal expansion in current flow direction can be approximated by Eqns 8 and 9

$$\Delta z = \Delta z_{hotzone} + \Delta z_{cold} = \int_{T_{start}}^{T_{high}} \alpha(T) \cdot z_{hotzone} \cdot dT + \int_{T_{start}}^{T_{low}} \alpha(T) \cdot (l - z_{hotzone}) \cdot dT \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta z = \int_{T_{low}}^{T_{high}} \alpha(T) \cdot z_{hotzone} \cdot dT + \int_{T_{start}}^{T_{low}} \alpha(T) \cdot l \cdot dT \quad (9)$$

The extension of the hot-zone can be estimated by integrating Eqn 9, using a measured $\Delta z = 60\mu\text{m}$, $T_0 = 25^\circ\text{C}$, $T_{low} = 55^\circ\text{C}$, $T_{high} = 120^\circ\text{C}$, $l = 15\text{mm}$, and $\alpha(T)$ from Fig.2. This results in an extension of the hot-zone $z_{hotzone} \approx 1.5\text{mm}$, which is about 10% of the total length of the PTC element.

Fig. 7: The current (dashed line) and the expansion of a test sample (full line) of HDPE5261Z composite material, are shown within a time window of 10ms. After reaching the maximum expansion of $65\mu\text{m}$, mechanical oscillations are observed around the new stable position of the sample at about $50\mu\text{m}$ elongation.

The temperature induced expansion reaches a maximum elongation and oscillates little later with a small amplitude around a stable extended position. The center part of the PTC-body develops the highest temperature. Due to the strong decrease of Young's Modulus of polyethylene when approaching the melting point, the center part of the PTC (the hot-zone) may be the region of largest mechanical deformations during the oscillations.

From the mechanical oscillations around the stable Δz -position of the expanded PTC sample the calculation of the Young's Modulus of the hot-zone is possible. The oscillation around the new stable position can be approximated by a harmonic oscillator with frequency f and amplitude Δx . In Eqn 10, m denotes the total accelerated mass, a is the acceleration, D the spring constant of the used brass terminal and $Y_{hotzone}$ is the mean Young's Modulus of the composite material inside the hot-zone. The cross-section of the hot-zone is assumed to be constant $A_{hotzone} \approx 0.5\text{ cm}^2$ for simplification.

$$F = m \cdot a = m \cdot 4\pi^2 \cdot f^2 \cdot \Delta x = \left(\frac{Y_{hotzone} \cdot A_{hotzone}}{z_{hotzone}} - D \right) \cdot \Delta x \quad (10)$$

A mean Young's Modulus of the hot-zone can be determined by using the measured frequency $f = 460\text{Hz}$, $m = 0.014\text{kg}$, $D = 11\text{kN/m}$ and $z_{\text{hotzone}} = 1.5\text{mm}$. Eqn 10 yields $E_{\text{hotzone}} = 3.84\text{MPa}$, which is less than 0.5 % of the value of the pure polyethylene at room temperature.

CONCLUSION

The combined on-line measurement of electrical current and mechanical motion, combined with the monitoring of the surface temperature by an infrared detecting system is a powerful tool to investigate the impact of locally generated thermal shock waves in structured composite materials. The technique correlates the thermally stimulated mechanical expansion of the composite to the heat generation and transport in the electrically conducting composite material. The combined measurement gives an interesting insight to the interaction of the electrical, mechanical and thermal properties of electro-composites.

The calculations yield a length of about 1.5mm for the hot-zone with an average Young's Modulus of about 4MPa.

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